

THE REPRESSIVE POLICY IN THE KASHKADARYA OASIS IN THE 20s AND 30s OF THE 20th CENTURY

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Abstract: This article examines the repressive policies implemented by the Soviet authorities against the Uzbek people in the Kashkadarya oasis during the 1920s and 1930s. It explores the activities of punitive organs in this region, the list compiled in 1935 by Heinrich Yanovich Weide, head of the Kashkadarya District Police Department, as well as the mass repressions of farms carried out from December 1928 to 1933.

Keywords: Soviet state, Kashkadarya oasis, Weide's list, J. Stalin, repression policy, kulaks, basmachi.

The political developments that occurred in the 1920s and 1930s removed the Romanov dynasty from power in Russia, which had ruled the country as an autocracy for three centuries. This period also saw the outbreak of revolution in the colonies, with the national territories experiencing repeated difficulties due to the oppression of the former imperial regime. Since the establishment of the so-called Red Kingdom, the USSR has never ceased its internal struggles, its oppression of its own people, and its pursuit of a policy of repression. The persecution was temporarily halted during the Second World War (1941-1945), which was initiated by Nazi Germany. After the war, the former Red Empire continued its repressive practices on an even larger scale. Leaders came and went, but there was no significant change in the policy of violence, national oppression, and suppression towards the Soviet-controlled territories. Instead, oppression of the people, exploitation of women, class-based persecution, suppression of religion, a retrograde view of history, and humiliation of national identity all continued from the late 1930s until the dissolution of the USSR in 1991. This period was characterized by a lack of respect for human rights, freedom, and national self-determination. The saddest aspect of the situation was the damage done to national spirit by the despotic regime, which aimed to destroy the best and most patriotic representatives of our country. While it is possible to rebuild stolen wealth, nothing can replace the talented compatriots who were unjustly executed and imprisoned. The suffering of hundreds of thousands of rural farmers

who were humiliated and labeled as "hostile elements" or "kulaks" cannot be consoled.

The rich, including priests, mullahs, former officials, and merchants, were eliminated as a class, leaving everyone impoverished. The Soviet state lasted for about 74 years, during which time its people were constantly oppressed and repressed. No other state in history has existed for such a long period without ever relieving the oppression of its people. Thus, the policy of repression pursued by the Soviet Union also affected Uzbekistan, one of its remote regions. In the 1920s and 1930s, there were bodies of political repression operating in the areas of the Kashkadarya oasis.

Kashkadarya is a large southern oasis in Uzbekistan, which for centuries was part of the Bukhara Emirate. After the fall of the emirate, a counter-revolutionary organization emerged in the region. This organization fought against the Soviet government until 1926. The struggle for freedom and against collectivization delayed the realization of Soviet goals for several years.

In the Kashkadarya oasis, from 1920 to 1940, there was an active struggle against the Soviet regime. Agriculture and animal husbandry were the main sources of livelihood in this oasis. Due to the harsh climate, people had to work hard to survive. There were no overly rich or poor in the oasis.. In a region like Kashkadarya, where endless steppes and deserts stretch out, it is unlikely to find a single wealthy cattle breeder with more than three thousand sheep, let alone ten thousand or five thousand. Heinrich Yanovich Weide, the head of the Kashkadarya District Police Department, who served from March 1935 to March 1936, compiled a list of former officials of the Emir, clergy, merchants, and wealthy households in the Kashkadarya region at the end of August 1935, on behalf of the District Party Committee. The disposition of these individuals was carried out in a prompt and large-scale manner in connection with the Land and Water Reform in the region from December 21, 1928, to the end of January 1929. The Land and Water Reform in Kashkadarya resulted in the liquidation of over 9,000 farms belonging to farmers, former officials, clergy, and merchants.¹¹

Until 1928, seizures of property belonging to enemies of the Soviet government were carried out not under the pretext of "dispossession," but rather under the banner of "eliminating accomplices of Basmachi (anti-Soviet insurgents)." After the land and water reforms, attacks on villages did not cease, but rather continued in a systematic

¹¹ Равшанов П. Қизил салтанат исқанжасида. Тажовуз.(Хужжатлардаги тарих) Уч жилдлик. Биринчи жилд. - Т.:Sharq, 2011, Б.13.

and intense manner. The list of Weide includes 1,416 farms that were dispossessed from 8 districts within the district. In 1925, the expropriation of one farm was recorded. This may have been an error, as since 1924, no list of expropriated farms has been compiled, which would indicate which properties were taken from "Basmachi collaborators", but these individuals were arrested or executed, and records were not maintained on them, so their numbers were only recorded in party and Soviet documents in a general sense. The list also includes the names of heads of 11 farms expropriated in 1926 and 11 farms liquidated in 1927. Expropriations of 22 farms over two years across the district cannot accurately reflect the true situation. This figure is highly relative, and we can assume that these were the only ones that were preserved in police records. It can be safely assumed that more than 90% of those expropriated on the list were from families with below-average means of subsistence. Two oxen were required for plowing land, and oxen were not a sign of wealth, but rather a vital necessity for plowing fields. Horses and camels, both working animals, were not considered luxuries for peasants and cattle breeders in their everyday lives. Most of the impoverished had horses, cows, oxen, sheep, and goats as well as donkeys. A few people owned camels, who were involved in trade and livestock farming. Camels served as a form of living transportation at the time, and goods were transported through them to distant countries. In the list, Suyun Kholmurodov, from the village of Ok-Rabata, is mentioned as owning a horse and a sheep, despite being impoverished. As with the aforementioned individuals, it becomes evident that the primary goal of the Soviet government was to impose a regime that forced our entire nation to live in poverty under the guise of reform.¹²

Dispossession and repression of farms that had "become wealthy without labor" and were seen as "parasitic" for having accumulated property through the exploitation of others' labor became widespread in Kashkadarya in December 1928 and peaked in 1933, as evidenced by Weide's records. During the last decade of 1928, 104 farms were dispossessed. In early January 1929, 116 more were dispossessed; in 1930, 262; in 1931, 138; in 1932, 126; and in 1933, 127. The end of March 1933 saw a period of "massive arrests," with Eshna Avazov, head of a sole proprietorship in the village of Kizil Tom, being an example of one who did not avoid persecution despite having been dispossessed in 1928. His house, three oxen, three horses, two cows, 130 sheep, and 180 acres of land were all confiscated, and he was arrested during a wave of arrests in March 1933 due to failing to meet a grain delivery target of 100 pounds.

¹² Равшанов П. Қизил салтанат исканжасида. Тажовуз.(Хужжатлардаги тарих) Уч жилдик. Биринчи жилд. - Т.:Sharq, 2011, Б.18.

The systematic policy of expropriation did not leave any family "deserving of expropriation" for 7-8 years. This was also the work of the special commission established in each district to search for and identify Kulak farms.¹³ The punitive authorities, similar to the period of the Basmachi movement, regularly provided operational information about agricultural activities of cooperatives and collective farms to higher authorities. The Kulaks and well-off individual farms were completely under their control, and their crops, words, and behavior were not neglected.

It is difficult to even imagine the extent of the wealth that was looted in Uzbekistan during Soviet occupation. The property that was seized under the guise of land and water reforms was also immeasurable. In the late 1920s, wealthy individuals from the lower regions of Kashkadarya were brought to the village of Jainov and forced to surrender their gold under extreme duress. Similar incidents occurred in Karshi, Shakhrisabz, Yakkabag, and Kitab. For the dispossessed, freedom was uncertain, as they could become prisoners at any time on unexpected charges.

In the 1920s and 1930s, the Kashkadarya region pursued a policy of extreme violence and repression. This included the destruction of forces fighting for freedom against the Soviet regime, as well as the elimination of hardworking and enterprising peasants as a class. This repression, which was based on social origin, led to significant national losses for our people.

The Soviet government was driven by the desire to accumulate wealth and plunder the resources of the country. As a result, it targeted those who stood in its way, including private property owners, and used women as cheap labor.

If World War II had not occurred, the repression in Kashkadarya would have continued unabated. Without the intervention of Hitler and the start of the war with Stalin in 1941, the Red Empire likely would not have ceased its oppression of the people. This is evident from the fact that, after the war in the early 1950s, repression against the intellectuals of the national periphery resumed. To attribute repression solely to I. Stalin is a one-sided approach. Even after his death, "dissidents" were persecuted and the most prominent among them were consistently subjected to repressive measures. This was the main goal of socialism as laid out by V. Lenin and, regardless of who governed, subordination to the Communist Party and implementation of a system based on violence were political priorities. This trend continued during the reign of N. Khrushchev when, in an attempt to catch up with the

¹³ Равшанов П. Қизил салтанат исқанжасида. Тажовуз.(Хужжатлардаги тарих) Уч жилдлик. Биринчи жилд.- Т.:Sharq, 2011, Б.19

US, a policy of criminal fraud led to the persecution of hundreds of thousands of Party, Soviet, and economic leaders in the USSR. Even Brezhnev's leadership was not free from repressive measures, as it was not in the nature of socialism to improve the lives of the people.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the suppression of the “attribution”, which became widespread in the first half of the 1980s, had a particularly significant impact on Uzbekistan. The “Uzbek case” and the “Cotton case” were deliberately exaggerated, which paved the way for a new massacre. Fortunately, this was the final repression. At the end of August 1991, Soviet power collapsed. Our homeland, Uzbekistan, regained its status as an independent state. The joy of independence cannot be compared to any other joy. Even the treasures of the world cannot determine the value of freedom. The faces of those who achieved this benefit is bright, and their future is bright and prosperous. For the sake of the memory of our fathers and grandfathers, who sacrificed their lives for freedom and suffered repression, we, representatives of the younger generation, must cherish and preserve this invaluable good.

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